

Dual-use technical products: a toolkit for expert assessment of their commercialization possibilities

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Аннотация. Для поступательного экономического роста отечественного оборонно-промышленного комплекса необходимы внебюджетные финансовые поступления, получаемые от рыночной реализации технической продукции двойного назначения, которая может быть использована как в военной, так и в гражданской сферах. Разработан комплексный непротиворечивый инструментарий для комплексной экспертной оценки возможности коммерциализации данного вида изделий на основе их классификации и кластеризации, а также оценки их технического потенциала. Разработанный экспертный инструментарий может быть использован предприятиями, выпускающими продукцию оборонного и гражданского назначения. Он позволит существенно повысить рентабельность и производительность предприятий оборонно-промышленного комплекса.

Abstract. Progressive economic growth of the national military-industrial complex requires off-budget financial revenues derived from the market realisation of dual-use technical products that can be used in both military and civilian spheres. A complex consistent toolkit has been developed for complex expert assessment of the possibility of commercialisation of this type of articles based on their classification and clustering as well as evaluation of their technical potential. The developed expert toolkit can be used by enterprises producing defence and civilian products and will significantly increase the profitability and productivity of military-industrial complex enterprises.

Ключевые слова: техническая продукция двойного назначения, военно-промышленный комплекс, экспертиза, коммерциализация.

Keywords: dual-use technical products, military-industrial complex, expertise, commercialisation.

Introduction

Russian and world experience convincingly confirms that additional income can be generated through the market sale of dual-use technical products (DUTP) manufactured by the national military-industrial complex (MIC) for due military organisation of the state and that can be used in many civilian production sectors of the economy [1, 2, 3, 4].

When collecting, accumulating and extending the aggregate data and knowledge bases about dual-use technical products, there is a need for constant and continuous expertise by the developers and customers of these products for identifying, evaluating and clarifying the prospects for their market commercialisation.

The reasons for this phenomenon are rooted, in the first place, in the great variety of conditions and possible areas of their practical application which do not allow for permanent use of generalised detailed forms and unified economic descriptions of these products contained in information bases leading to vagueness of specification, and, secondly, in the continuous and significant variability of internal and external economic and political situations requiring regular and mandatory clarification and adjustment of economic estimates of revenues from these items'

use in the civilian sphere and from their sale on the national and world markets.

Conceptual foundations of expert judgement

Since clustering as a research method is widely and actively used to accelerate economic development in various production spheres [5, 6], it is reasonable to apply it to expert examination of various DUTP. In modern conditions, the main purpose of expert examination of DUTP which is the basis for justifying managerial decisions regarding their sale and commercial distribution should not focus on detailed and direct economic evaluation of the product but rely on preliminary clustering (grouping) and systemic classification of DUTP with regard for the organisational and economic mechanisms and real conditions of these products' commercial distribution and potential sales as well as the methods of additional off-budget MIC funding based on production and market sales. Further, following the clustering and classification, more detailed and sophisticated evaluation methods should be applied which will take into account all features of any product and any sales process as well as the efficiency of use and distribution of the generated DUTP.

Given the peculiarities specific to the modern world economy, the following main features of DUP clustering and classification are the most important:

- expected terms and rates of additional financial returns from market sales of DUTP;
- scope of investment required to manufacture products in a commercialisable form (licences, patents, serial production);
- the opportunity to obtain additional financial investment for the realisation of defence orders following the DUTP's market sale on the global and national markets.
- potential risk situations and uncertainties arising from the sale of dual-purpose products in commercial, financial and technical aspects [7];
- long-term or short-term timeframe for DUTP producer's receipt of due financial assets as well as economic return from commercial realisation of the discussed products.

DUTP clustering

At the first stage of expert evaluation of each of the listed considerations, it is necessary to rank the dual-purpose products as assessment objects for the generation of clusters (groupings) which will be used in the future to carry out in-depth and more detailed analysis by various specially developed instrumental methods, simultaneously drawing up comprehensive and detailed business plans and specifying the source data.

Practice confirms that the number of basic clusters required for expert evaluation in case of a large number of assessed objects should not exceed 714 (otherwise, one can often face problems regarding the meaningful (conceptual) interpretation of being-created clusters as well as the problems of placing the evaluated objects in a particular cluster). The possible number of clusters, with three different states distinguished in each of them and six main independent attributes used (the attribute's high, medium and low level), reaches 729, which is unacceptable for practical use.

To create due conditions allowing to use the clusters with positive effect, it is necessary to reduce the number of cluster-forming attributes from six to three and additionally to reduce the number of identified possible states to two for each attribute (high and low level). It is recommended to use the first three attributes from the ones proposed above as the main attributes (terms and rates of additional financial returns, scope of required investment, and possibility of obtaining additional financial investment). The impact of changes in the remaining two attributes (potential risk situations and uncertainties, long-term or short-term timeframe) should be used within the main clusters.

Thus, using the proposed conceptual framework for expert judgement, eight main clusters should be created for grouping technical products.

Cluster 1. It encompasses DUTP that initially do not require a great amount of necessary investments and guarantee the customer's substantial income and quick return of the spent resources (the

most optimistic option). This class includes well-tested, competitive and innovative technical products used for various purposes, those covered by an exhaustive set of technical documentation, licences and patents, securing great opportunities for the conclusion of cooperation agreements, normally having no security restrictions on replication and commercial distribution and characterised by high market sale prospects.

Cluster 2. This cluster encompasses DUTP that do not require substantial initial investments, guarantee the customer's quick return on the spent resources but yield only a small financial return. This case looks similar to the first one, but the principal difference includes the limited use of the products, great distribution spread or the existence of conditions connected with property rights, which reduces the expected number of sales.

Cluster 3. It encompasses DUTP that initially do not require substantial investments and guarantee the customer's sizeable income, being characterised by a relatively slow rate of additional revenues and a lengthy timeframe for receiving economic returns from the commercial sale of the products. This cluster includes items similar to those in the most optimistic cluster but not yet characterised by the complete cycle of scientific research and industrial production or clear prospects of concluding cooperation agreements with the civilian sector for the organisation of co-funding processes and joint realisation of all scheduled works.

Cluster 4. It encompasses DUTP that do not require a large initial investment, but at the same time do not allow for a substantial financial return for the customer and are characterised by a relatively slow rate of yielding additional financial returns. In a sense, this cluster is similar to the previous one, but is characterised by large-scale distribution and wide applicability of the manufactured products; it also abides by the owner's rights.

Cluster 5. This cluster encompasses DUTP which require a large initial investment but guarantee the customer's great revenues and quick return on the expended resources. This cluster includes some products specific to the first cluster, those involving the sale of licences and patents. It is expedient and useful for the customer, upon their serial industrial production, to actively participate in their further sale and joint work with licence buyers.

Cluster 6. This cluster encompasses DUTP that promise a quick return on expended resources but require a large initial investment and do not guarantee substantial financial returns to the customer. This cluster includes some products from the previous cluster, but the customer's involvement in the processes of practical use of patents and licences as well as investment activities is insignificant.

Cluster 7. It encompasses DUTP that guarantee substantial financial returns to the customer but require sizeable initial investment and are characterised by a long-term period of economic return. This cluster includes some products similar to those in

cluster 5 but characterised by the incomplete research and industrial production process cycle, requiring investments realised over a lengthy period.

Cluster 8. It encompasses DUTP that require a large amount of initial investment, do not guarantee the customer's sizeable revenues and are characterised by a long-term economic return timeframe. This cluster is similar to the previous one in many respects but is characterised by the inactive participation of the customer in the production and market sale of the products. The customer participates in these processes under the condition of minimal financial, commercial and technical risks.

It is necessary to emphasise quite an important feature of the process of classifying and including products into different clusters. The products under evaluation may simultaneously fall into different clusters and be perceived (analysed) in them independently of each other depending on the production funding, the extent of the customer's involvement in their development and sale, and the peculiarities of their consideration and assessment rate.

Methods of DUTP distribution into clusters

Scientifically justified clustering of products should be performed by experts using the following most significant parameters: expected scale of usability (narrow usability in one industry or sphere for handling a certain class of objectives, usability in several industries or spheres for solving different tasks, wide usability for many industries or spheres for resolving any tasks); estimated level (traditional, medium, high, groundbreaking); product development level (completed or incomplete research cycle); product development level (complete or incomplete); availability of licences, patents, prototypes, patent protection reliability, product's industrial realisation degree); expected timeframe for the completion of scientific research, design and development, as well as the practical realisation of the product; the required amount of investments (in general and by stages) and their payback; types of expected effects (economic, financial, social, environmental); legal and other restrictions on the product transfer for use in certain areas or spheres; potential buyers of the product (domestic public and commercial sector, foreign public and commercial sector); assessment of the state of the global and national markets; any preliminary agreements and arrangements for the production and sale of the products [8, 9, 10].

DUTP clustering based on the above indicators can be effectuated straightforwardly or using various formalised methods.

In the case of direct clustering of products, the expert, using the information systematised according to the proposed indicators, categorises the products into the clusters he/she has chosen based on his/her own informal and formal methods. When using formalised methods, the expert merely checks the indicators and the source data for the items under consideration. Products are assigned to specific clusters on the basis of patterns and dependencies common to all DUTP.

Matching of parameters specific to high-level products, for example, widespread distribution in many spheres and areas, availability of production prototypes, licences and patents, as well as products' short payback period automatically results in the DUTP's inclusion in the first (optimistic) and fourth clusters. Any available supplementary information on the secondary (additional) areas of practical use, on high prospects of market sales or the possibility of concluding cooperation agreements with foreign economic entities, means the possibility of including the DUTP in the third and penultimate (seventh) clusters.

At the same time, matching parameters specific to high-level products, such as limited practical use and an incomplete cycle of scientific research and industrial production, results in the product falling into the third, fifth or sixth clusters.

Product clustering may be followed by a more detailed and thorough examination considering the factors of uncertainty, commercial and technical risks, assessing the prospects for the emergence and formation of cooperative ties, identifying inaccuracies in the initial data and errors in the estimated figures of required financial and resource investment.

This initial stage of DUTP's expert evaluation allows, already at the preliminary stage of the analysis, to essentially specify and clarify the possibilities and most efficient ways of their commercialisation and to set additional methods for their further, more accurate, analysis.

Assessment of the commercial and technical potential of DUTP

Currently, the scientific and methodological substantiation and the development and practical use of modern methods of off-budget funding of state defence orders and commercial projects remain a relevant and important problem of the national MIC development [11]. The need for research addressing this problem is accounted for not only by the anti-Russian sanctions, the critical state of many industrial sectors [12, 13] and the low GDP of the state but also by the integration of Russian enterprises and corporations into the global system of production of various-purpose items and some international financial organisations.

It should be particularly noted that the development of new innovative methods and models using military/economic analyses [14] towards improving the commercial and technical potential of defence enterprises was hampered at the beginning of the 21st century by the crises in the Russian economy and the emergence of numerous financial and organisational difficulties in their practical use that could not be surpassed at that time [15, 16].

For these reasons, quite often, the expert process can be focused on obtaining the products' generalised characteristics apart from the problems of direct clustering of items for their more detailed and thorough analysis within the boundaries of selected groups. Such characteristics are traditionally represented by indicators of integrally assessed DUTP's commercial and technical potentials.

The following method of products' integral evaluation is possible:

- each level is assigned a specific rating (e.g. traditional – 1, medium – 2, high – 3, groundbreaking – 4);

- similarly, ratings are assigned to potential product distribution areas (e.g. traditional – 3, limited – 2, insignificant – 1);

- evaluating the product level and distribution enables the expert to assess the integral commercial and technical potentials (e.g. groundbreaking in a narrow area – 4, high with large-scale distribution and use – 9, etc.).

Depending on the actual product development state at a given time and with regard for its integral commercial and technical resource, its current potential can be estimated at the next step. For this purpose, the indicators of integral commercial and technical potentials are multiplied by a coefficient characterising the actual (in-progress) development stage.

Further, using the data on DUTP's integral and current commercial and technical potentials and considering the additional information on potentially likely sales markets, the necessary scope of investments and expected rates of their actual return, their actual values at each point in time can be determined.

Conclusion

Given the large number of dual-use technical products as well as the complexity of their complex assessment, the systemic expert examination procedure requires the development of research and software-implemented information systems as well as computerised workstations for experts.

The main objects of such expert systems include DUTP clustering with regard for their potential and advantages, efficiency and prospects of market commercialisation, scope of DUTP's commercial and technical potential, both in aggregate clusters and within each formed cluster, as well as the identification of the most promising products in each cluster through the use of special tools ensuring more accurate technical, economic and marketing assessment.

Of particular importance in the modern complex conditions of the ongoing special military operation [17] is the development of systemic regulations for the pre-investment evaluation of future DUTP sales; the main stages of this evaluation can be formulated as follows: preparation of necessary data, preliminary study of specific characteristics of the products to be sold, comprehensive marketing study of DUTP purchase forecasts from the perspective of specific buyers; financial, economic and budgetary analysis of all the planned DUTP commercialisation processes for military products customers and setting the work structure for every stage.

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